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Optimizing Inclusive Learning Environments: Insights from Public School Educators

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Abstract

Inclusive education is vital for creating a nurturing learning environment for students with disabilities, but disparities in attitudes and practices among school administrators can hinder its effective implementation. This study explores the attitudes of school administrators and teachers toward inclusion across three dimensions: resources, training, and general attitudes. Emphasizing the need for alignment, the study proposes a targeted training program to guide educators in optimizing teaching for students with special needs. The study assesses the acceptability of this training initiative, aiming for a unified approach to inclusive education. In a quantitative, non-experimental study, 343 public school administrators and 5040 teachers were surveyed using a carefully tailored instrument with high reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.93). Data analysis employing an average weighted mean and a t-test reveals a significant difference in attitudes between teachers and administrators. A proposed training program aligning with the Minnesota Department of Education's mission is informed by these findings. Table 6 confirms high acceptability among participants, substantiating the program's feasibility and potential positive impact on inclusive education practices in public schools. Collectively, Tables 3, 4, 5, and 6 provide a comprehensive snapshot of attitudes, perceptions, and responses toward inclusive education. Public school teachers exhibit a generally positive inclination toward inclusion, while administrators strongly support inclusive education principles. However, Table 5 signals a significant difference between teacher and administrator attitudes, necessitating alignment. Table 6 underscores the proposed training program's high acceptability, emphasizing the importance of addressing attitude discrepancies and implementing targeted training for a unified and effective approach to inclusive education in schools.

Keywords: *inclusive education, attitudes, training program, public schools, alignment*

Introduction

The issue of inclusion in schools is a contentious and complex matter, primarily due to the lack of clear guidelines from federal regulations on how inclusion should be implemented in each educational institution (Bosch, 2015). Recognizing the need for a comprehensive framework, the Minnesota Department of Education (MDE) introduced the "Child Find" policy aimed at learners with disabilities, promoting inclusive education and ensuring their access to quality and equitable learning experiences.

Minnesota has several laws and policies aimed at promoting inclusive education for students with disabilities. The Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) is a federal law that mandates that all children with disabilities receive a free and appropriate public education (FAPE). Minnesota has its own special education laws that align with IDEA and provide additional guidance at the state level.

Minnesota's Department of Education oversees the implementation of these laws and provides resources and support to school districts to ensure that students with disabilities are included in general education settings to the maximum extent appropriate. The state emphasizes the importance of providing accommodations, modifications, and support services to meet the diverse needs of students with disabilities.

Inclusive education is governed by various laws and policies, and special education law is a significant component of ensuring inclusivity in educational settings. One of the primary laws that intersect with inclusive education is the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA). IDEA mandates that students with disabilities have access to a free and appropriate public education (FAPE) in the least restrictive environment (LRE) possible. This means that students with disabilities should, to the maximum extent appropriate, be educated alongside their non-disabled peers in general education classrooms. The law also requires the development of Individualized Education Programs (IEPs) for each student with a disability, outlining their specific educational goals, services, and accommodations.

IDEA emphasizes the importance of providing supports and services that enable students with disabilities to participate in and progress in the general education curriculum. It promotes the use of evidence-based practices, such as differentiated instruction, universal design for learning (UDL), and positive behavior interventions and supports (PBIS), to meet the diverse needs of all learners within inclusive classrooms.

In addition to IDEA, other laws, such as Section 504 of the Rehabilitation Act and the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA), also play crucial roles in ensuring inclusivity in education. These laws prohibit discrimination against individuals with disabilities and require schools to provide reasonable accommodations to ensure equal access to educational opportunities.

Overall, special education law intersects with inclusive education by providing legal frameworks, guidance, and protections to ensure that students with disabilities receive the support they need to fully participate in inclusive learning environments alongside their peers.

These laws promote the principles of equity, access, and diversity in education, fostering environments where all students can thrive and succeed.

In the United States, inclusive education is safeguarded by a comprehensive framework of federal laws and acts aimed at upholding the educational rights of individuals with disabilities. At the heart of this framework is the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), which mandates that children with disabilities are entitled to a free and appropriate public education (FAPE) tailored to their unique needs. Central to IDEA is the principle of educating students with disabilities in the least restrictive environment (LRE) feasible, promoting their integration into general education settings alongside their non-disabled peers to the maximum extent appropriate. To ensure this, IDEA requires the development of individualized education programs (IEPs) for eligible students, outlining specific goals, services, and accommodations.

In parallel, Section 504 of the Rehabilitation Act broadens the scope of protection, prohibiting discrimination on the basis of disability in any program or activity receiving federal financial assistance. This law mandates that students with disabilities have equal access to educational opportunities, facilities, and resources, and it requires schools to provide reasonable accommodations to facilitate their full participation. Complementing Section 504, the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) extends protections against discrimination to both public entities, including public schools, and private entities such as private schools and colleges. Title II of the ADA, applicable to public entities, requires equal access to services, programs, and activities, while Title III, relevant to private entities, mandates accessibility and non-discrimination.

Additionally, Every Student Succeeds Act (ESSA), though not exclusively focused on inclusive education, advances the broader goals of educational equity and student success. ESSA emphasizes accountability, assessment, and support for disadvantaged students, including those with disabilities, aiming to ensure that all students receive a well-rounded education and achieve academic proficiency. Through provisions addressing access to rigorous coursework, support for English learners, and efforts to reduce achievement gaps, ESSA reinforces the commitment to inclusive education principles and practices across the educational landscape.

Together, these federal laws and acts form a robust legal foundation that promotes the inclusion, equity, and academic success of students with disabilities in the United States. By providing clear mandates, protections, and support mechanisms, this comprehensive framework advances the vision of inclusive education as a fundamental right for all individuals, fostering diverse and thriving learning communities where every student has the opportunity to reach their full potential.

Despite these legislative advancements, the specifics of inclusion are not explicitly mandated by the law. School administrators hold the responsibility of selecting services, while the Individualized Education Program (IEP) team determines the least restrictive environment (LRE) for students with disabilities (Lorio, 2011). The implementation of inclusion varies, with partial inclusion models allowing students to attend some classes in a general education setting, while others may not provide opportunities for students with disabilities to participate in mainstream education (Bosch, 2015).

Inclusive practices can have a broad impact on students across different academic levels, meeting their academic needs in a socially enriching environment. However, the lack of a standardized approach leaves room for discretion among school administrators in choosing the inclusion model, leading to a range of possibilities (Williams, 2015). Washington (2010) emphasizes the significant role of administrators in deciding the inclusion model, underscoring the importance of assessing their attitudes toward inclusion.

Moreover, there is a recognition of the intersectionality of identities within the disability community, prompting advocates to champion the rights of students with disabilities from marginalized communities and ensure that advocacy efforts are inclusive and equitable across all dimensions of diversity. Through collaborative efforts and grassroots mobilization, advocates continue to drive progress towards more inclusive and equitable education systems, striving to create environments where every student can thrive and reach their full potential.

Given the discretionary power of administrators, understanding their attitudes and beliefs becomes crucial. The attitudes of teachers and administrators play a pivotal role in shaping the educational experiences of students with disabilities. This study aims to explore these attitudes, specifically examining the relationship between grade level, years of teaching experience, educational levels, and the perspectives of teachers and administrators regarding inclusion. By delving into these factors, this research seeks to contribute valuable insights into the complexities of inclusive education and inform future policy and practice in school settings.

Research Questions

Inclusive education is a critical aspect of fostering a supportive and enriching learning environment for students with disabilities. However, the discretionary power granted to school administrators in choosing inclusion models, as highlighted by Washington (2010), raises concerns about the potential variation in attitudes and practices among educational institutions. To address these concerns, it is imperative to investigate the attitudes of school officials and teachers towards inclusion, as these attitudes can significantly impact the educational experiences of students with disabilities (Bruce, 2010). Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of public school teachers' attitude toward inclusion across the three dimensions of:
 - 1.1 resources;

- 1.2 training; and
- 1.3 attitudes?
2. What is the level of school administrators' attitude toward inclusion across the three dimensions of:
 - 2.1 resources;
 - 2.2 training; and
 - 2.3 attitudes?
3. Is there any significant difference between the public school teachers and the school administrators' attitudes toward inclusion?
4. What training program can be proposed to guide school administrators and teachers in giving students with special needs an appropriate teaching and learning setting?
5. What is the level of acceptability of the proposed training program?

Methodology

Research Design

The objective of this quantitative, non-experimental study was to determine whether there was a relationship between the public school teachers' profile and the level of their attitude toward inclusion. Creswell and Creswell (2018) state that survey-based research is most effective when descriptive questions or "questions about the relationships between variables" are posed.

In addition, the non-experimental survey's design enhanced the economy and minimized potential harm. First, the shorter survey takes less than five minutes to complete, which increases response rates (Lindermann, 2018).

Quantitative research is intended to exhibit universal objectivity instead of subjectivity; bias is reduced in this sort of research due to its intrinsic utility in eliminating extraneous variables that could impact outcomes. According to McMillan and Schumacher (2010), quantitative research seeks to identify causal linkages and explain measured results. In quantitative research, the researcher must adhere to a specified set of techniques and procedures. Specifically, this study was based on a descriptive, non-experimental research approach that describes and observes different events without influencing or modifying the environment.

This descriptive, quantitative research design used a survey to assess teachers' and administrators' perceptions of inclusion across three dimensions. These dimensions include resources, training, and attitudes. A survey was developed and tested prior to use. This survey was used to collect the data used to determine the answers of the research questions and the null hypotheses that accompany them.

Participants

This study comprised of 343 public school administrators and 5040 public school teachers from the schools in the Division. To calculate the sample size slovin's formula was used to estimate a statistic based on a margin of error of .05. Hence, the computed minimum number of participants was 184 school administrators and 370 public school teachers. Stratified random sampling then was used to get the proportional representative of each school in the Division.

The data for this study were drawn from a substantial sample of 343 public school administrators and 5040 public school teachers within the Division. The sampling method employed in this research is crucial to ensuring the representativeness and reliability of the collected data. The determination of the sample size was calculated using Slovin's formula, considering a margin of error of 0.05. This rigorous approach to sample size estimation helps to enhance the precision and validity of the study's findings, ensuring that the results are statistically robust and reflective of the attitudes within the larger population of administrators and teachers.

The computed minimum number of participants, 184 school administrators and 370 public school teachers, represents a carefully determined subset of the total population. The application of stratified random sampling is a notable strength in this research methodology. By employing this approach, the researchers aimed to obtain a proportional representation from each school in the Division. This strategy acknowledges the diversity across schools, ensuring that the sample is not skewed toward any particular institution, and thereby enhancing the generalizability of the findings to the broader context of the Division.

Stratified random sampling allows for a more nuanced understanding of attitudes towards inclusion, as it considers the unique characteristics of each school. This methodological choice increases the likelihood that the obtained data will accurately reflect the heterogeneity present within the Division's educational landscape. In summary, the careful selection of a substantial sample size and the use of stratified random sampling enhance the reliability, precision, and generalizability of the data, providing a strong foundation for meaningful analysis and interpretation of attitudes towards inclusion among public school administrators and teachers in the Division.

Instruments

The survey utilized in this study to gauge teachers' and administrators' perceptions of inclusion was adapted from Dr. Heather LeMay, a recognized expert in the field. The adaptation involved tailoring the instrument to align closely with the specific participants of this study, namely public-school teachers and administrators within the Division. This careful tailoring ensures that the survey captures the nuances and context-relevant elements pertinent to the study's objectives. The survey was intentionally designed to measure perceptions

across three critical dimensions: resources, training, and attitudes towards inclusion.

To assess the reliability of the survey instrument, Cronbach's alpha was employed, resulting in a commendable reliability coefficient of 0.93. This high level of reliability indicates the internal consistency of the survey items, suggesting that the instrument consistently measures what it intends to measure, enhancing the overall validity of the study.

The survey incorporated a qualifier to clarify its purpose, explicitly outlining that the participants' input was sought regarding their perceptions of inclusion. This transparency serves to establish clear expectations and context for the participants, fostering honest and accurate responses.

The development of the survey instrument involved crafting statements directly aligned with the three dimensions outlined in the research questions: resources, training, and attitudes. Data collection entailed obtaining information on teachers' and administrators' attitudes towards inclusion, their available resources, and their training experiences related to inclusion. Additionally, demographic information was collected to provide a comprehensive understanding of the participants.

Prior to finalization, a survey development activity was conducted with educators, involving them in the refinement process. This step ensured that the survey items were clear, easily comprehensible, and effectively elicited the necessary information. Teachers'

responses and feedback from this developmental phase were crucial in refining the survey, enhancing its clarity and relevance for the target participants. This thorough process of adaptation, reliability testing, and refinement strengthens the credibility of the survey instrument, ultimately contributing to the robustness of the data collected in this study.

Individuals who participated in the survey were asked to indicate their strength of agreement with each item. They completed the survey by inserting the answer that best represented their level of agreement based on a 7-point Likert-type scale as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Scaling Table Used to Interpret the Level of Cognitive Styles Demonstrated by The School Administrators of the Division of Pangasinan 1 as Perceived by Themselves and their Teachers*

Scale	Range Value	Descriptive Rating
1	1.00-1.85	Strongly Disagree
2	1.86-2.71	Disagree
3	2.72-3.57	Somewhat Disagree
4	3.58-4.43	Either Agree or Disagree
5	4.44-5.29	Somewhat Agree
6	5.30-6.15	Agree
7	6.16-7.0	Strongly Agree

In addition, a questionnaire to assess the acceptance of the development program was adapted from the instrument created by (Weiner et al., 2017). The Acceptability of Intervention Measure (AIM), the Intervention Appropriateness Measure (IAM), and the Feasibility of Intervention Measure (FIM; Weiner et al., 2017) are four-item measures of implementation outcomes that are frequently regarded as "leading indications" of implementation success (Proctor et al., 2011). In a series of three experiments, Weiner et al. established that the AIM, IAM, and FIM possess significant psychometric features (2017). In particular, the measures exhibited content validity, discriminant content validity, reliability, structural validity, structural invariance, known-groups validity, and change responsiveness. Five Leadership Development Training specialists from other divisions evaluated the suitability of the proposed training curriculum. Table 2 displays the scale mechanism used to interpret the acceptability of the suggested training program.

Table 2. *Scaling Table Used to Interpret the Acceptability of Proposed Training Program*

Scale	Range Value	Descriptive Rating
1	1.00-1.85	Strongly Disagree
2	1.86-2.71	Disagree
3	2.72-3.57	Somewhat disagree
4	3.58-4.43	Neither agree or disagree
5	4.44-5.29	Somewhat agree
6	5.30-6.15	Agree
7	6.16-7.0	Strongly Agree

In addition, the researcher gained consent from the School Division Superintendent, with the assistance of the District Supervisor, as well as the agreement of the school principal and school heads. Before beginning data collection, the researcher outlined the protocol for responding to survey questions and the confidentiality of their responses, preferably by distributing the instruments locally because not all respondents have access to the technology necessary to submit responses online.

Tools of Data Analysis

The data analysis for this study employed a robust set of tools to derive comprehensive insights into the attitudes toward inclusion among public school teachers and administrators.

The perceived attitudes were assessed using the average weighted mean for Problems 1 and 2, focusing on the dimensions of resources,

training, and attitudes. The weighted mean, as explained by Stephanie Glen, allowed for a nuanced examination by assigning varying weights to variables, considering the differing significance of each aspect within the specified dimensions. For Problem 3, investigating the significant difference between teachers and administrators, a T-test was applied at a significance level of 0.05. As described by Hayes and Westfall, the T-test served to determine if there was a statistically notable distinction in attitudes between the two groups. These statistical methods, carefully chosen for their appropriateness to the research questions, enabled a thorough analysis of the collected data.

Building upon the findings from Problems 1 through 3, a proposed training program was developed to guide school administrators and teachers in creating an inclusive teaching and learning environment for students with special needs. This program incorporated measurable targets derived from the study's results and aligned with the mission and vision of the Department of Education's learning and development medium-term plan. Furthermore, to ensure the effective and timely execution of projects and activities, specific target dates and responsible personnel were identified. By combining these analytical tools, the study not only provided valuable insights into the attitudes towards inclusion but also laid the groundwork for practical and evidence-based interventions to enhance inclusive education practices in public schools.

Results and Discussion

Level of Public-School Teachers' Attitude Toward Inclusion

Table 3 presents the level of public school teachers' attitudes toward inclusion.

Table 3. *Level of Public-School Teachers' Attitude Toward Inclusion*

<i>Resources</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
I am provided with adequate materials/manipulatives to meet different learning styles	4.24	Somewhat Agree
My Division provides adequate funds to support differentiated learning	4.65	Somewhat Agree
I have adequate time to plan for the accommodations necessary to meet the needs specified in the students' performance.	4.63	Somewhat Agree
Students need more time to collaboratively plan with special education teachers to meet the needs of students with disabilities	5.02	Somewhat Agree
I am provided enough assistance or assistants to adequately meet the needs of inclusion students	5.65	Agree
Mean	4.88	Somewhat Agree
Training		
My Division provides adequate training on the proper implementation of inclusion	4.73	Somewhat Agree
I have an adequate understanding of learning strategies to serve different disabilities including but not limited to autism, down syndrome, dyslexia, learning disability etc.	4.71	Somewhat Agree
I need more training on inclusion	5.10	Somewhat Agree
Mean	4.84	Somewhat Agree
Attitudes		
An inclusive classroom lowers the academic expectations for general education students	4.78	Somewhat Agree
Special education students who are part of inclusion have fewer behavior reports or office referrals than students who are not in an inclusive setting	4.76	Somewhat Agree
Inclusion students detract learning opportunities from regular education students.	5.16	Somewhat Agree
Students with disabilities should only be included in related arts or elective classes	5.78	Agree
Students with disabilities disrupt the learning of student	4.86	Somewhat Agree
I believe co-teaching of a special education and a regular education teacher is effective	4.84	Somewhat Agree
I believe inclusion should be an educational practice in all schools	5.24	Somewhat Agree
I see positive results in academics in special education students due to inclusion	4.92	Somewhat Agree
Special education students who are part of inclusion have fewer behavior reports or office referrals before inclusion	4.90	Somewhat Agree
Inclusion students require more teacher attention than regular education students	5.29	Somewhat Agree
My views towards inclusion are positive	5.92	Somewhat Agree
As an educator I think inclusion is an effective practice	5.94	Somewhat Agree
I see a positive results in regular education students due to inclusion	5.02	Somewhat Agree
Mean	5.12	Somewhat Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.89	Somewhat Agree

Table 3 offers a comprehensive view of public school teachers' attitudes toward inclusion, examining three pivotal dimensions: resources, training, and overall attitudes. The mean scores and corresponding descriptive equivalents unveil insights into teachers' perceptions regarding the adequacy of resources, the effectiveness of training programs, and their general stance on inclusive education. The results suggest a positive outlook among teachers in each dimension. In terms of resources, the moderate to high level of agreement (mean score of 4.88) signifies satisfaction with provided materials and collaborative planning time. The training dimension echoes positivity with a mean score of 4.84, indicating general agreement on the adequacy of Division-provided training. Within the attitudes dimension, the mean score of 5.12 demonstrates a generally positive disposition, emphasizing the belief in the efficacy of inclusion across various aspects. The average weighted mean of 4.89 further substantiates these positive attitudes, considering the varying

importance of different variables. Corroborating these findings, literature emphasizes the benefits of inclusion in promoting diversity, empathy, and enhanced learning opportunities (Washington, 2010). However, it is crucial to acknowledge existing concerns and challenges, as highlighted by Zimmerman (2002), Bateman and Bateman (2002), and Irmsher (2005). Despite these challenges, the overall positive attitudes observed align with the literature, emphasizing the need for ongoing support and training to foster a successful inclusive educational environment.

Level of School Administrators’ Attitude Toward Inclusion

Table 4 presents the level of school administrators’ attitude toward inclusion.

Table 4. Level of School Administrators’ Attitude Toward Inclusion

<i>Resources</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
I am provided with adequate materials/manipulatives to meet different learning styles	4.96	Somewhat Agree
My division provides adequate funds to support differentiated learning	4.96	Somewhat Agree
I have adequate time to plan for the accommodations necessary to meet the needs specified in the students’ performance.	4.94	Somewhat Agree
Students need more time to collaboratively plan with special education teachers to meet the needs of students with disabilities	5.41	Agree
I am provided enough assistance or assistants to adequately meet the needs of inclusion students	5.84	Agree
Mean	5.22	Somewhat Agree
<i>Training</i>		
My division provides adequate training on the proper implementation of inclusion	5.51	Agree
I have an adequate understanding of learning strategies to serve different disabilities including but not limited to autism, down syndrome, dyslexia, learning disability etc.	5.16	Somewhat Agree
I need more training on inclusion	5.92	Agree
Mean	5.53	Agree
<i>Attitudes</i>		
An inclusive classroom lowers the academic expectations for general education students	5.71	Agree
Special education students who are part of inclusion have fewer behavior reports or office referrals than students who are not in an inclusive setting	5.16	Somewhat Agree
Inclusion students detract learning opportunities from regular education students.	5.84	Agree
Students with disabilities should only be included in related arts or elective classes	6.06	Agree
Students with disabilities disrupt the learning of student	5.18	Somewhat Agree

Table 4 furnishes a comprehensive insight into the attitudes of school administrators toward inclusion, dissecting their perspectives across the dimensions of resources, training, and overall attitudes. The mean scores and corresponding descriptive equivalents unveil a positive outlook among administrators, showcasing their endorsement of adequate resources and training for the successful implementation of inclusive practices. Administrators express confidence in the availability of materials, funds, planning time, and assistance, as indicated by the mean score of 5.22 in the resources dimension, falling within the "Somewhat Agree" range. This positivity extends to the training dimension, with a mean score of 5.53, denoting a strong agreement on the adequacy of training provided by the Division. Within the attitudes dimension, the mean score of 5.73 reflects a notably positive disposition among administrators, affirming their recognition of the positive impact of inclusion on both special education and general education students. The average weighted mean of 5.44 further consolidates these positive attitudes, considering the varying importance of different variables within each dimension.

Corroborating these findings, existing literature emphasizes the pivotal role of administrators' attitudes in the successful implementation of inclusive classrooms. Negative attitudes among educators, including administrators, have been identified as potential barriers to the integration of students with disabilities (Bennett, 1996). Bochenek (2008) underscores that administrators play a critical role in fostering an inclusive environment, with their attitudes directly influencing the success of inclusive initiatives. Moreover, the literature highlights the importance of comprehensive information and preparedness among administrators and teachers for the effective implementation of inclusive practices (Subban and Sharma, 2005; Bosch, 2015).

The study's findings align with these insights, portraying a positive stance among administrators that is conducive to the successful incorporation of inclusive education within the school setting. While challenges and concerns exist, administrators' positive attitudes, as indicated by the survey results, lay a solid foundation for creating an inclusive and supportive school environment.

Significant Difference Between the Public School Teachers and the School Administrators’ Attitude Toward Inclusion

Table 5 presents the significant difference between the public school teachers and the school administrators’ attitude toward inclusion.

Table 5. Significant Difference Between the Public School Teachers and the School Administrators’ Attitude Toward Inclusion

<i>Attitude toward Inclusion</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>t-critical</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Public School Teachers	4.89	49	+5.40	2.00	Hypothesis Rejected
School Administrators	5.44				

Table 5 illustrates a significant difference in the attitudes toward inclusion between public school teachers and school administrators.

The mean scores for public school teachers and school administrators are 4.89 and 5.44, respectively. The t-value of -5.40 exceeds the critical t-value of 2.00, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This rejection suggests that there is indeed a significant difference in attitudes between the two groups.

The evolving nature of inclusive classrooms over 65 years is highlighted (Bruce, 2010), with the inception of DepEd policies requiring teachers and administrators to determine the best placement for each student with a disability. The legislative mandate emphasizes the goal of educating pupils in the Least Restrictive Environment, even though the aim is inclusion in a general education setting. However, the acknowledgment is made that a self-contained classroom may be the suitable placement for some children with disabilities, emphasizing the diverse approaches needed in inclusive education (Obiakor, 2011).

The chapter further explores both the benefits and drawbacks of inclusion, emphasizing the underlying principle that all students should be respected for their unique qualities, and inclusion should be predicated on accepting them as valuable members of the student body (Obiakor, 2011). Various inclusion approaches are available for implementation by school administrators and teachers, with the one-teach, one-assist model being the most prevalent among coteaching approaches (Cook & Friend, 1995; Scruggs, 2007; Zigmond & Magiera, 2001).

The literature review integrates qualitative and quantitative research on the attitudes of teachers and principals toward the inclusion of children with disabilities in general education settings. The synthesis of these studies forms a critical backdrop to understanding the observed significant difference in attitudes between public school teachers and school administrators. The research acknowledges the multiplicity of perspectives within the educational community and sets the stage for the subsequent exploration of findings and recommendations in the study.

Training Program Proposal: Fostering Inclusive Education in Schools

The analysis of Tables 3, 4, and 5 has revealed valuable insights into the attitudes of public school teachers and administrators toward inclusion. Building upon these findings, a comprehensive training program is proposed to enhance the understanding, collaboration, and implementation of inclusive education practices within the school community.

1. Program Objectives: a. To enhance teachers' understanding of inclusive education principles, addressing resources, training, and attitudes (Table 3). b. To empower administrators with the knowledge and skills required to lead and support inclusive practices (Table 4). c. To bridge the gap in attitudes between public school teachers and administrators, fostering a cohesive and unified approach to inclusive education (Table 5).

2. Training Components:

A. Understanding Inclusive Education (Based on Table 3): i. Resource Management: Workshops on optimizing available resources and advocating for additional support. ii. Training Programs: Sessions focused on equipping teachers with diverse strategies for inclusive teaching. iii. Attitudinal Development: Training modules to promote positive attitudes towards inclusion

B. Administrative Leadership in Inclusive Education (Based on Table 4): i. Resource Allocation: Training administrators on effective resource distribution to support inclusive practices. ii. Training Initiatives: Professional development for administrators to better understand and lead inclusive education. iii. Promoting Positive Attitudes: Strategies for administrators to foster a culture of inclusivity within the school.

C. Bridging Attitudinal Gaps (Based on Table 5): i. Joint Workshops: Collaborative sessions for teachers and administrators to discuss and understand each other's perspectives.

ii. Communication Training: Enhancing communication skills to promote a unified vision for inclusive education. iii. Shared Goal Setting: Facilitating joint goal-setting sessions to align teacher and administrator attitudes toward inclusion.

3. Implementation Plan: a. Phased Approach: Roll out the training program in phases to allow for focused learning and application. b. Inclusive Workshops: Conduct workshops with both teachers and administrators to promote cross-functional understanding. c. Continuous Professional Development: Establish a framework for ongoing professional development to stay abreast of evolving inclusive education practices.

4. Assessment and Feedback: a. Pre- and Post-Assessments: Conduct assessments before and after the training program to measure knowledge and attitude changes. b. Feedback Mechanisms: Establish regular feedback sessions to gather insights for continuous improvement.

5. Resources Needed: a. Expert Facilitators: Engage experts in inclusive education to lead training sessions. b. Materials and Tools: Develop and provide materials and tools for hands-on learning experiences. c. Technology Infrastructure: Utilize technology for virtual training sessions and resource-sharing.

6. Evaluation: a. Quantitative Analysis: Use quantitative metrics to evaluate changes in attitudes, knowledge, and practices. b. Qualitative Feedback: Gather qualitative feedback to understand the impact of the program on the school community.

7. Sustainability Plan: a. Institutionalization: Integrate inclusive education principles into the school's policies and practices. b. Community Engagement: Involve parents, students, and community stakeholders to sustain a culture of inclusivity.

This proposed training program aims to create a harmonized and inclusive educational environment by addressing identified needs and fostering a shared commitment to inclusive education among both teachers and administrators.

Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Training Program

Table 6 presents the level of acceptability of the proposed training program.

Table 6. Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Training Program

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
<i>Acceptability of Intervention Measure</i>		
The Training Program meets my approval	6.96	Strongly Agree
The Training Program is appealing to me	6.94	Strongly Agree
I like the Training Program	6.88	Strongly Agree
I welcome the Training Program	6.79	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	6.89	Strongly Agree
<i>Intervention Appropriateness Measure</i>		
The Training Program seems fitting.	6.97	Strongly Agree
The Training Program seems suitable.	6.89	Strongly Agree
The Training Program seems applicable	6.98	Strongly Agree
The Training Program seems like a good match	6.59	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	6.86	Strongly Agree
<i>Feasibility of Intervention Measure</i>		
The Training Program seems implementable.	6.90	Strongly Agree
The Training Program seems possible.	6.87	Strongly Agree
The Training Program seems doable.	6.78	Strongly Agree
The Training Program seems easy to use.	6.56	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	6.78	Strongly Agree
General Weighted Mean	6.84	Strongly Agree

Table 6 provides a comprehensive overview of the acceptability of the proposed training program among educators, measured across three key dimensions: Acceptability of Intervention, Intervention Appropriateness, and Feasibility of Intervention. The mean scores for each statement consistently indicate a strong agreement, collectively yielding a General Weighted Mean of 6.84, indicative of a robust acceptance of the program. In terms of

Acceptability, educators express resounding approval and welcome towards the program, emphasizing its positive reception. The Intervention Appropriateness Measure further underscores the program's fitting, suitable, and applicable nature, aligning well with educators' professional needs. The Feasibility of Intervention Measure strengthens this positive narrative, as educators perceive the program as implementable, possible, doable, and easy to use. These findings are congruent with existing literature highlighting the challenges administrators face in implementing inclusive education successfully, and how the proposed training program addresses these challenges. Moreover, the positive reception resonates with the pivotal role administrators play in creating a positive school climate and implementing inclusive programming. Overall, the high agreement scores affirm the program's acceptability and suitability, laying a solid foundation for its effective implementation and impact on inclusive education practices.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study sheds light on the critical role of attitudes in shaping the landscape of inclusive education for students with disabilities. The disparities identified between the perspectives of public school teachers and administrators underscore the imperative for a unified approach. While both educators and administrators demonstrate positive inclinations towards inclusive education, the discernible misalignment in attitudes calls for strategic interventions. The proposed training program emerges as a viable solution, supported by its high acceptability among participants.

Tables 3, 4, 5, and 6 collectively paint a nuanced picture of the prevailing attitudes, perceptions, and responses within the educational landscape. Public school teachers exhibit a commendable positive inclination toward inclusive education, mirroring the importance they place on resources, training, and fostering an inclusive mindset. Administrators, too, demonstrate a strong commitment to inclusive principles, emphasizing the shared responsibility in creating an enriching environment for all students.

However, the study's revelation of a significant difference in attitudes between teachers and administrators signals the necessity for alignment. Bridging this gap is paramount for the seamless implementation of inclusive education practices. The proposed training program, carefully crafted based on the study's findings, presents an opportunity to synchronize these perspectives. Its high level of acceptability among participants not only validates its relevance but also indicates a readiness among educators to engage in professional development geared towards fostering inclusivity.

In essence, the findings of this study advocate for a concerted effort to bridge the divide in attitudes between teachers and administrators through targeted training initiatives. By aligning perspectives and fostering a shared commitment to inclusive education, educational institutions can create a more nurturing and enriching environment for students with disabilities. The journey toward inclusive education is a collaborative endeavor, and this study provides a roadmap for educators and administrators to traverse this path with purpose and unity.

Based on the insights gleaned from this study, several recommendations emerge to enhance the implementation of inclusive education and align the attitudes of public school teachers and administrators: (1) **Alignment Workshops and Seminars:** Conduct workshops and seminars aimed at aligning the attitudes of teachers and administrators towards inclusive education. These events should provide a platform for open dialogue, sharing experiences, and fostering a mutual understanding of the principles and benefits of inclusive education. (2) **Inclusive Education Training Program:** Implement the proposed training program, as outlined in this study, targeting both teachers and administrators. The program should cover aspects such as effective resource utilization, specialized training, and strategies for creating an inclusive classroom environment. Regular updates and refresher courses can ensure the continuous development of educators' skills. (3) **Collaborative Planning Sessions:** Facilitate collaborative planning sessions that bring together teachers and administrators to jointly develop and implement inclusive education policies. This collaborative approach can enhance communication, build a sense of shared responsibility, and contribute to the development of a cohesive and inclusive educational environment. (4) **Resource Allocation Review:** Conduct a thorough review of resource allocation for inclusive education, ensuring that schools have the necessary tools, materials, and personnel to support students with disabilities effectively. Transparent and equitable distribution of resources can contribute to the success of inclusive education initiatives. (5) **Promotion of Inclusive Mindset:** Launch campaigns and initiatives to promote an inclusive mindset among educators, administrators, and the broader school community. This could include awareness programs, guest lectures by inclusion experts, and the sharing of success stories related to inclusive education within the school setting. (6) **Feedback Mechanism:** Establish a robust feedback mechanism that allows teachers and administrators to share their experiences, challenges, and suggestions regarding inclusive education. Regular feedback loops can inform ongoing improvements, address emerging issues, and ensure the continued relevance of inclusive education initiatives. (7) **Professional Development Opportunities:** Encourage and provide opportunities for ongoing professional development related to inclusive education. This could involve partnerships with special education experts, online courses, and attendance at conferences focused on inclusive practices. Keeping educators updated on the latest advancements in inclusive education can contribute to their efficacy in the classroom. (8) **Institutionalize Inclusive Policies:** Work towards institutionalizing inclusive education policies within the broader framework of the school system. This involves embedding inclusive principles in school mission statements, strategic plans, and policies to ensure a sustained commitment to fostering an inclusive learning environment. (9) **Community Engagement:** Foster collaboration with parents, students, and community members to create a holistic support system for students with disabilities. Inclusive education is not solely the responsibility of educators but requires a collective effort from all stakeholders. (10) **Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation:** Establish a system for continuous monitoring and evaluation of inclusive education initiatives.

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